

THE INTERFACES OF GF/UP SYSTEMS AND THE MICROSCOPIC RHEOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The coupling agent content and thickness on glass fibre surfaces which have been treated with silanes and titanates under different conditions are measured by means of XRF (X-Ray Fluorescent spectrometry). And the rheological characteristics of the dispersed systems prepared from the above glass fibres combined with unsaturated polyester resin are discussed. The results show that the rigidity of the internal layers of silane coupling agents absorbed by glass surfaces is greater than the external layers; while the effect of the titanate coupling agents on the rheological characteristics of the system is approximately the same in each structural layer, which is due to the fact that both the internal and external layers of titanates on glass surfaces have the similar flexible structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many workers have presented their research reports which deal with the rheological characteristics of fibre/polymer dispersed systems. In their further studies, Bretas and Powell¹ found that the silane $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{Si}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$ on glass surfaces and the $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHOTi}(\text{OCOC}_{17}\text{H}_{35})_3$ in glass microcell/PE or PVC dispersed system appear different effect on the rheological characteristics of the systems, to which they said they could not explain.

The thickness of coupling agents absorbed by glass surfaces is so thin that it cannot affect the aspect ratio α_r of glass fibres in the system. Therefore, it is mistaken to consider that the variations occurred in rheological characteristics are caused due to macroscopic reasons. In my research, I have discussed in detail the effect of the bonding forms of coupling agents with glass surfaces and the molecular structures of coupling agents upon the rheological characteristics in the systems; meantime I has also dealt with the effect of temperature. Thus, I explained the phenomenon found by Powell et. al.^{2,3}

A lot of experiments show^{4,5} that the coupling agents absorbed on glass surfaces have a multilayer structure. Nevertheless there has been still no research upon the relation between the properties of each structural layer of coupling agent on glass surfaces and the rheological characteristics of the dispersed system. Taking this into consideration, the Author decide in this paper to make a discussion upon the rheological characteristics of the dispersed system so as to do an analysis upon the structural properties of coupling agent layers in the interfaces.

2. EXPERIMENT

2.1 Instrument

PW1410 X-ray diffraction-fluorescent spectrometer (Philippe Cor.) and 3063 X-ray fluorescent spectrometer (Ligaku, Japan) are used for doing the X-ray fluorescence analysis. NXS-11 rotation viscometer (Chengdu Instrument Factory, China) is used to do rheological experiment.

2.2 Materials

Both unsaturated polyester resin (UP) and glass fibres (GF) used in the experiment are supplied by Changzhou 253 Factory of Building Materials (China). UP used is 189# of density 1.17g/cm³; GF used is E-glass having a diameter of 9 micrometers; the glass powder is obtained by grinding glass marbles (specific gravity: 2.65g/cm³). The median diameter (50wt% average) of the glass powder is 24.3 micrometers and the specific surface area 1798cm²/g which are measured with a micrometer photographic filler meter.

The names and chemical structures of the coupling agents used in the experiment are listed in table 1.

Table 1 Names and chemical Structures of Coupling Agents

Trade name	Chemical name	Chemical structure	Density
A-172	Vinyltris(β-methoxyethoxy)silane	CH ₂ =CHSi(OCH ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₃) ₃	-
A-1100	γ-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane	H ₂ N(CH ₂) ₃ Si(OCH ₂ CH ₃) ₃	-
A-174	γ-Methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane	CH ₂ C=CO(CH ₂) ₃ Si(OCH ₃) ₃ CH ₃ O	1.045
TTS	Isopropyl triisotearoyl titanate	(CH ₃) ₂ CHOTi[OCOCH(CH ₂) ₁₄ CH ₃] ₃ CH ₃	1.095
NDZ-301	Di(dioctylphosphato)ethylene titanate	CH ₂ -O \ Ti [OPO(OC ₈ H ₁₇) ₂] ₃ CH ₂ -O /	-

2.3 Experimental method

2.3.1 Surface treatment of glass fibres

Firstly, glass fibres are cut into 1/8 inch in length and are boiled in distilled water for three times, each for half an hour. Having been dried, they are washed with ketone (under boiling state) for three times, each for half an hour. Again they are dried, and then their surfaces are treated with coupling agents. Silanes and water are mixed into 1wt% silane water solutions; titanates and petroleum ether are mixed into 1wt% titanate petroleum ether solutions. The treatment conditions of various samples are shown in table 2 and table 3. The dried untreated fibres are called No.0. Each samples is dispersed in detail and preparing rheological samples.

Table 2 Samples Treated with Silanes

Treatment condition	Sample number \ coupling agent		
	A-172	A-174	A-1100
Fibres impregnated in silane solution for 0.5 minute, then dried	1-172	1-174	1-1100
Samples No.1(above) washed in cool water for half an hour, then dried	2-172	2-174	2-1100
Samples No.2 boiled in water for half an hour, then dried	3-172	3-174	3-1100

Table 3 Samples Treated with Titanates

sample number Treatment condition	coupling agent	
	TTS	NDZ-301
Fibres impregnated in titanate solution for one minute, then dried	1-TTS	1-NDZ
Samples No.1 washed with petroleum ether for 5 minutes, then dried	2-TTS	2-NDZ
Samples No.2 refluxing extracted for half an hour, then dried	3-TTS	3-NDZ

2.3.2 Testing of coupling agent content on fibre surfaces

Glass powder is sufficiently mixed with titanium dioxides (TiO_2) with different titanium content. Then it is pressed into tablets which are used for measuring X-ray fluorescence intensity Q_{Ti} of titanium. Thus, the relation graph (Fig.1) of fluorescence Q_{Ti} with respect of titanium content is drawn as a standard curve. Under the conditions listed in table 3, glass powder is treated with TTS solutions. Then it is pressed into tablets which are used for measuring X-ray fluorescence intensity Q'_{Ti} . Thus the titanate content and thickness are calculated from the standard curve.

Glass powder is sufficiently mixed with KBr with different bromine content. Then it is pressed into tablets which are used for measuring X-ray fluorescence intensity Q_{Br} of bromine. Thus, the relation graph of fluorescence intensity Q_{Br} with bromine content is drawn as a standard curve (Fig.1). Glass powder is treated with A-174 solution (into which the same equivalence of bromine water solution is added) under the condition given in table 2. Then X-ray fluorescence intensity Q'_{Br} of bromine of samples is measured. Now, silane coupling agent content and thickness can be obtained according to Fig.1.

Fig.1 Relation of Br, Ti content and Q_{Br} , Q_{Ti}

2.3.3 Preparation of samples and testing of their rheological characteristics

The fibre content in the sample is obtained to be 0.15wt% according to the results of the former research⁶. Then it is stirred for 2 hrs. and is left at rest for the escape of bubbles for 2 hrs.

At first, samples are preheated at the testing temperature. And then their rheological properties are tested at constant temperature. The error of preheating and testing temperature should be maintained in the range of $\pm 0.05^\circ C$.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Structural layers of coupling agents on the glass surfaces

The X-ray fluorescence spectra of the glass powders treated with two types of coupling agents are shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3. In table 4 are

shown the fluorescence intensity Q'_{Ti} and Q'_{Br} as well as the coupling agent content and thickness of different samples calculated from the standard curves, specific surface area of glass powder and the density of coupling agents.

Table 4 Coupling agent content on glass powder surfaces

sample number*	Q'_{Ti}	Q'_{Br}	coupling agent content of glass powder surface per unit weight (g/g)	thickness of coupling agent layer δ (nm)
untreated F-0		background intensity		
		4605	0	0
F-1-174		586733	8.12×10^{-3}	43.2
F-2-174		244463	3.34×10^{-3}	17.8
F-3-174		65243	8.45×10^{-3}	4.5
untreated F-0	background intensity			
	3201		0	0
F-1-TTS	8439		1.83×10^{-2}	92.1
F-2-TTS	6521		1.16×10^{-2}	59.0
F-3-TTS	3471		7.48×10^{-4}	3.8

* "F" represents glass powder sample

The specific surface area of glass fibre calculated is $S_r = 1677 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ which is similar to one of the glass powder. It can be considered that surface free energy of a material is related only with specific surface area⁷, so it is reasonable to think that glass powder has the same activity as glass fibre owing to their same specific surface area.

A-174 content and thickness δ on glass powder surfaces shown in table 4 mean the one of brominated A-174. Supposing that A-174 has the same activity before and after bromination (i.e. before and after bromination, Si-OH groups possess the same activity and can be absorbed by glass surface similarly), the data in table 4 will be the content and thickness of A-174 and TTS on glass surfaces.

It can be seen from δ data in table 4 that coupling agents have formed several structural layers on fibre surfaces, each having different bonding strength and among which only can the extremely thin inner layer be absorbed on glass surfaces.

3.2 Influences of different structural layers of coupling agents on rheological characteristics of GF/UP systems. Glass fibre is treated with several kinds of coupling agents and the rheological graphs of GF/UP systems are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5.

Fig.2 X-ray fluorescence spectra of bromine in glass powder treated with brominated A-174.

Fig.3 X-ray fluorescence intensity of titanate in glass powder treated with TTS

Fig.4 Rheological characteristics of GF/UP systems (250°C)
 ○ no treatment; × washed with cool water;
 ● impregnation; Δ washed with boiling water.

Fig.5 Rheological characteristics of GF/UP systems (25°C)
 ○ no treatment; ● impregnation treatment;
 Δ extracted with petroleum ether;
 × washed with petroleum ether at ambient temperature.

It is seen from δ data in table 4 that coupling agents (in spite of any kind) on fibre surfaces all will not change the cross-longitudinal ratio δ_r of fibre. Therefore, from the macroscopic rheological point of view, they must not affect the rheological characteristics of the systems. However, it is clearly shown in Fig.4 that the rheological characteristics of GF/UP systems obviously vary as the thickness of silane layer changes, and this is certainly caused by the interfacial effect of the interface materials.

It is found in Fig.4 that silanes when existing on fibre surfaces will lead to a worse flowability for the treated GF/UP system than for the untreated system. It has been pointed out in the former reports that this is because the silane coupling agent have formed a rigid frame on glass surfaces which will cause a higher inner friction with resin matrix³. Fig.5 shows that the flowability of GF/UP system is improved by titanates. As Monte and Sygerman⁸ and Han et.al.⁹ have stated, this is because the titanates in interface range have reduced the interaction between the polymer long chains and thus result in a plastization effect. The Author think that the opposite effect of the two types of coupling agents can be further explained by the rigidity and deformability of the structural layers of the interfacial materials on glass surfaces³.

It can be found by further considering Fig.4 that the influences of the internal and external structural layers of silanes on glass surfaces on the rheological characteristics of the system are altered and the internal layer causes the flowability being worse than the external one. In my study, the Auther found that the external layers are easier to be permeated than the internal ones as the absorption layers of A-174 on glass surfaces are permeated with bromine water. Thus, it is considered that the internal layers of coupling agents on glass surfaces are rather dense, while the external ones very loose¹⁰. For the above reason, it is thought that the changes in the rheological characteristics of the system are brought about by the different structural layers of coupling agents on glass surfaces.

Because the silanes in external layers are looser than the ones in internal layers, the interval between the molecules of the former ones will be larger than the latter ones. Therefore, the external structural layers must have a greater deformability than the internal ones. Since the external structural layers which possess a greater deformability than internal ones under shearing stress allow a larger deformation, they will show a smaller inner friction with medium. This is obviously seen in Fig.4 where the flowability of the system becomes worse as the external layers on glass surfaces are eliminated one after another.

Glass fibre surfaces which are treated with two kinds of titanates and are further washed have shown similarly multilayer structures, but no difference is seen between their flowability in Fig.5. This is because that the titanates on glass surfaces are composed of linear flexible chains with great deformability. As a result, both the internal and external layers will carry on similar deformation, and the inner friction will not result in an obvious difference.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Different types of coupling agents (silanes and titanates) when existing in GF/UP interfaces will lead to varied interfacial effect in GF/UP systems under shearing stress. Coupling agents are found in multilayer structures on glass surfaces. Since silanes have built-up rigid frame structures and the internal structural layers are much denser than the external ones, the internal layers have larger rigidity and greater deformability under shearing stress as comparing with external layers; and thus the former ones will show a more considerable inner friction than the later as GF/UP systems are made to flow. Nevertheless, the different structural layers of titanates on glass surfaces result in similar effect on the systems owing to the similar flexibility of both internal and external titanate layers on glass surfaces.

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